

Equilibrium and Formation Constants of Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) Complexes of N-Benzoyl Phenyl Hydroxyl Amine in Various Mixed Aqueous Solvents

A. K. CHAUDHURY* and N. KOLE

Chemistry Department, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal

Manuscript received 5 June 1981, accepted 23 May 1982

The equilibrium constants $\beta = [ML][H]/[M][HL]$, where $M = \text{Co(II)}$, Ni(II) or Zn(II) ; $\text{HL} = \text{N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxyl amine (NBPHA)}$ and formation constant $\beta' = [ML]/[M][L]$ have been determined in five different mixed aqueous solvents namely, dioxane-water, isopropanol-water, acetone-water, ethanol-water and methanol-water in 75% v/v compositions. The order of equilibrium constants ($\log \beta_n$) are found to have no relation with $1/\epsilon$ sequence of the media, but is almost the same for different metal ions. The formation constants ($\log \beta'_n$), however, are in a sequence similar to $1/\epsilon$ sequence, with a few exceptions. In all the solvents the order of stability is $\text{Co(II)} > \text{Ni(II)} < \text{Cu(II)} > \text{Zn(II)}$. The anomalous position of Co(II) is attributed to Jahn Teller type of distortion.

In a previous communication¹ we reported in detail the interaction of Cu(II)-NBPHA complex system in various mixed aqueous solvents. The study has been extended to other metallic central ions e.g. Co(II) , Ni(II) and Zn(II) and the findings are presented here. The physical properties of Mn(II) , Co(II) , Ni(II) , Cu(II) or Zn(II) complexes of NBPHA were studied and their stability constants determined in 50% v/v dioxane-water by Bag and Lahiri². Shome *et al*³ reported the stabilities of Al^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} , Sc^{3+} , Y^{3+} and La^{3+} complexes of NBPHA in 50% dioxane-water.

In the present work equilibrium constants for the reactions $\text{M}^{2+} + \text{HL} = \text{ML}^+ + \text{H}$ etc., where $M = \text{Co(II)}$, Ni(II) or Zn(II) and $\text{HL} = \text{NBPHA}$, and formation constants for the reaction $\text{M}^{2+} + \text{L}^- = \text{ML}^+$ etc. have been determined in five different mixed aqueous solvents in 75% v/v composition. This high volume per cent composition was maintained to cope with the solubility difficulties, considering all the solvents. The object of the present study was to investigate the solvent effects on the stability of complexes of a series of metal ions and variation of formation and equilibrium constant of a metal complex with the variation of the nature of the solvent media.

Experimental

All reagents were of A. R. or G. R. grade. The composition of the experimental solutions were described in an earlier paper⁴. The titrations were carried out in 75% v/v dioxane-water (D-W), isopropanol-water (I-W), acetone-water (A-W), ethanol-water (E-W) and methanol-water (M-W) at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 M with NaClO_4 . The pH measurements were made with a bench model Cambridge

pH meter using glass electrodes. True [H] concentration was measured as before⁴.

The equilibrium constants, β_1 and β_2 , for the reactions

were calculated as reported earlier^{1,4,5}. The formation constants, β'_1 and β'_2 , were also calculated by the earlier reported method^{1,4,5} using the relations

$$\begin{aligned} \log \beta_1 &= \log \beta'_1 - \log {}^pK_1^{\text{H}} \\ \log \beta_2 &= \log \beta'_2 - 2 \log {}^pK_1^{\text{H}} \quad \dots (2) \end{aligned}$$

The computation was done in BURROUGHS 6700 system as described before⁴.

Results and Discussion

$\log \beta_1$, $\log \beta_2$, $\log \beta'_1$ and $\log \beta'_2$ and ${}^pK_1^{\text{H}}$ values for Co(II) , Ni(II) and Zn(II) are set out in Table 1. Values of Cu(II) are taken from the previous paper¹ for comparison.

In 75% v/v solvent compositions the sequence of $1/\epsilon$ values is $\text{D-W} > \text{I-W} > \text{A-W} > \text{E-W} > \text{M-W}$. The values of $\log {}^pK_1^{\text{H}}$ have the sequence $\text{A-W} > \text{D-W} > \text{I-W} > \text{E-W} > \text{M-W}$. $\log \beta_1$, $\log \beta_2$, $\log \beta'_1$ and $\log \beta'_2$ have the following sequences for the different metal ions:

Cobalt(II):

TABLE I—EQUILIBRIUM AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) AND Cu(II) COMPLEXES OF NBPFA IN DIFFERENT MIXED AQUEOUS SOLVENTS AT $80 \pm 0.1^\circ$ AND 0.1M IONIC STRENGTH

Solvent composition	$1/\epsilon$	Mole fraction	$\log P K_1^H$	Metal ions	Equilibrium constants		Formation constants	
					$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta'_1$	$\log \beta'_2$
75% D - W	0.0699	0.388	10.59 ± 0.01	Co(II)	-3.29 ± 0.002	-7.77 ± 0.001	7.30 ± 0.012	13.41 ± 0.021
				Ni(II)	-3.41 ± 0.004	-8.15 ± 0.004	7.18 ± 0.014	13.03 ± 0.024
				Zn(II)	-3.03 ± 0.002	-7.25 ± 0.002	7.56 ± 0.012	13.93 ± 0.022
				*Cu(II)	-0.26 ± 0.004	-1.58 ± 0.004	10.33 ± 0.014	19.60 ± 0.024
75% I - W	0.0859	0.415	9.83 ± 0.01	Co(II)	-3.06 ± 0.014	-6.67 ± 0.01	6.77 ± 0.024	12.99 ± 0.03
				Ni(II)	-3.08 ± 0.011	-6.81 ± 0.008	6.75 ± 0.021	12.85 ± 0.028
				Zn(II)	-2.93 ± 0.02	-6.45 ± 0.01	6.90 ± 0.03	13.21 ± 0.03
				*Cu(II)	-0.08 ± 0.02	-1.44 ± 0.01	9.75 ± 0.03	18.22 ± 0.03
75% A - W	0.0289	0.422	10.67 ± 0.01	Co(II)	-3.51 ± 0.006	-7.94 ± 0.004	7.16 ± 0.016	13.40 ± 0.024
				Ni(II)	-3.58 ± 0.003	-8.36 ± 0.003	7.09 ± 0.013	12.98 ± 0.023
				Zn(II)	-3.46 ± 0.015	-7.43 ± 0.007	7.21 ± 0.025	13.91 ± 0.027
				*Cu(II)	-0.43 ± 0.03	-2.00 ± 0.02	10.24 ± 0.04	19.34 ± 0.04
75% E - W	0.0271	0.470	9.74 ± 0.01	Co(II)	-2.92 ± 0.01	-6.87 ± 0.005	6.82 ± 0.02	13.61 ± 0.025
				Ni(II)	-3.02 ± 0.007	-7.05 ± 0.004	6.72 ± 0.017	12.43 ± 0.024
				Zn(II)	-2.75 ± 0.007	-6.45 ± 0.006	6.99 ± 0.017	13.03 ± 0.026
				*Cu(II)	-0.27 ± 0.01	-1.46 ± 0.01	9.47 ± 0.02	18.02 ± 0.03
75% M - W	0.0230	0.573	9.57 ± 0.01	Co(II)	-3.18 ± 0.007	-7.57 ± 0.06	6.39 ± 0.017	11.57 ± 0.026
				Ni(II)	-3.21 ± 0.003	-7.86 ± 0.005	6.36 ± 0.013	11.28 ± 0.025
				Zn(II)	-3.12 ± 0.006	-7.23 ± 0.004	6.45 ± 0.016	11.91 ± 0.024
				*Cu(II)	-0.27 ± 0.01	-1.62 ± 0.01	9.30 ± 0.03	17.52 ± 0.03

* The values were reported earlier¹.

Nickel(II) :

$\log \beta_1$ —E-W > I-W > M-W > D-W > A-W
 $\log \beta_2$ —I-W > E-W > M-W > D-W > A-W
 $\log \beta'_1$ —D-W > A-W > I-W > E-W > M-W
 $\log \beta'_2$ —D-W > A-W > I-W > E-W > M-W

Zinc(II) :

$\log \beta_1$ —E-W > I-W > D-W > M-W > A-W
 $\log \beta_2$ —E-W > I-W > M-W > D-W > A-W
 $\log \beta'_1$ —D-W > A-W > E-W > I-W > M-W
 $\log \beta'_2$ —D-W > A-W > I-W > E-W > M-W

Copper(II) :

$\log \beta_1$ —I-W > D-W = E-W = M-W > A-W
 $\log \beta_2$ —I-W > E-W > D-W > M-W > A-W
 $\log \beta'_1$ —D-W > A-W > I-W > E-W > M-W
 $\log \beta'_2$ —D-W > A-W > I-W > E-W > M-W

The sequence of $P K_1^H$ is explained¹ as follows. Weak proton solvation of acetone puts acetone on the top. Although D-W has low dielectric constant, larger proton solvation by dioxane-water and also by the cosolvent removes dioxane from the first place to the second. The alcoholic solvents are in the sequence of their $1/\epsilon$ values. In addition, they are stronger proton solvating. That acetone water has a tendency to go higher up in the series is evident from the fact that in 75% v/v composition, although the mole fraction of A-W is a bit greater than that of D-W or I-W, it is much less than that of E-W or M-W. The difference between A-W and E-W is also very large although the difference in $1/\epsilon$ for these two compositions is quite small.

The equilibrium constants, $\log \beta_1$ and $\log \beta_2$, show random deviation from $1/\epsilon$ sequence. But one thing is remarkable. The sequences are almost unaltered by the different metal ions. Acetone-water generally has the lowest value since the cosolvent here has the least tendency to solvate proton. Alcohols go up in the sequence as they solvate protons comparatively to a larger extent.

The formation constants, $\log \beta'_1$ and $\log \beta'_2$, however have some correlation with the $1/\epsilon$ sequence in the different solvents, because proton solvation may not have here any direct influence. The order for $\log \beta'_1$ is less regular but $\log \beta'_2$ has become almost similar to the $1/\epsilon$ sequence, only that acetone-water and isopropanol-water have exchanged places. Here again, it may be noted that the nature of the metal ions has little effect on the order.

In every solvent-water system the stability sequence for metal ions is observed to be Co(II) > Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II). Co(II) is thus found to deviate from Irving and Williams' order. The entropy factor is likely to be similar in these systems. So it appears that it may be an evidence of Jahn Teller type of distortion for $t_{2g}^5 e_g^2$ set in high spin Co(II) ion ($t_{2g}^5 e_g^2$). This may be the reason for slightly higher stability of Co(II). Higher L.F.S.E. effect of NBPFA ligand may also be a contributory factor to this.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the grant of a Teacher Fellowship to one of them (N. K).

References

1. A. K. CHAUDHURY and N. KOLE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 368.
2. S. P. BAG and S. LAHIRI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 1611.
3. S. C. SHOME, M. R. SENGUPTA and H. R. DAS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 350.
4. A. K. CHAUDHURY, N. KOLE and S. P. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 243.
5. A. K. CHAUDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1236.